

IN-PLANE COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF HONEYCOMBS WITH NON-UNIFORM WALL THICKNESS AND CELL SIZE

Youmig Chen, Raj Das and Mark Battley

Department of Mechanical Engineering and Centre for Advanced Composite Materials, University
of Auckland, Auckland 1010, New Zealand
Email: cyou659@aucklanduni.ac.nz

Keywords: Irregular honeycombs, Compression, Cell size, Cell wall thickness, 3D printing,

ABSTRACT

As two dimensional cellular materials, honeycombs are often studied to aid understanding of the mechanics of cellular solids. However, regular honeycombs do not contain variations in microstructures which are ubiquitous in real cellular solids. Therefore, in this paper irregular honeycombs with cell wall thickness and cell size following lognormal distributions are manufactured using a 3D printer and utilized to study the compressive response of cellular solids. As the raw material used by the 3D printer is fairly brittle, these honeycombs fail by cell wall fracture. During the compressive tests, it is found that the deformation and failure progression in the irregular honeycombs are different from those in regular honeycombs, with cell walls rupturing gradually and at multiple locations. Cracks trace along weak cell walls, which are thin and long cell walls aligned with the compressive loading direction within the range of 30° to 60°. Additionally, short and thick cell walls may not only be resistant to fracture, but also strengthen their neighbouring areas and prevent their adjacent walls from rupturing. Stress reaches maximum soon after the first cell wall failure. The measured stiffness and strength of honeycombs with non-uniform cell wall thickness and cell size are considerably smaller than those of the regular honeycombs with the same relative density.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellular solids are increasingly being used in automotive, aerospace, aircraft, marine, construction and packaging industries due to their advantage in weight-saving, impact-absorbing, thermal-insulating, noise-abating and so forth. Hence, the mechanics of cellular solids has drawn a great deal of attention over the past few decades (refer to the work of Gibson [1-4] and Kyriakides.[5-9]) and a comprehensive review can be found in [10].

Cellular solids are indeed heterogeneous and most of them are anisotropic. The response of cellular materials to mechanical loads is also highly nonlinear and rate-dependent. In order to for engineers to use them safely and efficiently, characterizing the global properties of cellular solids is vitally important. Over the last decades, numerous experimental investigations have been carried out on the characterization of cellular solids of all kinds [11-16]. With extensive experimental data, it is recognized that the global properties of cellular solids is strongly related to relative density and the properties of base materials [10, 13]. Although cellular solids are viewed as homogeneous and continuous macroscopically, they are heterogeneous and discontinuous at cell level. Hence, the global response of cellular solids is dependent on their microstructures as well. Consequently, a great deal of effort has been directed into the study on the global properties-microstructure relationships of cellular solids [17-23]. Among them majority of work have been undertaken by numerical simulations, as cellular solids with specified microstructures are difficult to manufacture. However, these numerical models have idealized geometry different from realistic cellular solids, and thus validation using data from realistic cellular solids is not logically rigorous.

Honeycombs, as 'two dimensional' cellular solids, are often employed to study the mechanics of cellular solids due to their geometric simplicity. Knowledge gained from honeycombs can be extrapolated to three dimensional cellular solids. Papka and Kyriakides [5, 24] experimentally explored the compressive response of regular honeycombs. Deformation and failure patterns at cell level were well captured using a camera and subsequently linked to the global response of the

specimens. However, variations in microstructures are ubiquitous in cellular solids, such as irregular cell shape, non-uniform cell size and wall thickness. Therefore, it is more sensible to study the mechanics of cellular solids by using irregular honeycombs, such as honeycombs with random wall thickness and cell size which are more geometrically representative of realist cellular solids. Nevertheless, it is always a challenging task to manufacture honeycombs with non-uniform wall thickness and cell size. 3D printing technique has been significantly improved over the last few years, making it possible to manufacture these irregular honeycombs. In the present study, irregular honeycomb specimens (honeycombs with non-uniform wall thickness and cell size) will be manufactured using 3D printing technique. Subsequently, in-plane compressive tests will be carried out with a synchronized camera to capture the deformation and failure pattern at cell level. Lastly, failure modes in these honeycombs will be analysed and compared with those in regular honeycombs to understand the effect of variations in microstructure on the failure of cellular solids.

2 SPECIMEN DESIGN

All the specimens were manufactured by the 3D printer (Projet HD 3500 Plus), which has a net build volume of $203 \times 178 \times 152$ mm. The build material VisiJet M3 X is utilized. The highest printer resolution of $16 \mu\text{m}$ layers ($750 \times 750 \times 1600$ DPI (xyz)) was chosen in order to make the material as isotropic as possible. Three types of specimens were printed, including type I dogbone, regular and irregular honeycombs specimens. The specification of these specimens is presented in this section.

2.1 Dogbone specimens

Because 3D printers build parts by stacking a layer of materials on top of the previous layer, the properties of printed materials become anisotropic and differ from that of isotropic raw materials. Hence, the properties of materials printed need to be measured. To this end, dogbone specimens of type I were printed in three orthogonal orientations (see Figure 1a).

Figure 1: (a) printing orientations of dogbone specimens; (b) printed regular honeycomb

2.2 Regular honeycomb specimens

Regular honeycombs were printed in this work to verify if the printed honeycombs behaviour is the same as that of conventional honeycombs and to compare it with the response of printed irregular honeycombs. Two wall thickness-to-length ratios (0.025 and 0.05) are considered. The regular honeycombs of low thickness-to-length ratio are designed to fail by cell wall buckling, whilst the honeycombs of high thickness-to-length ratio are designed to fail either by cell wall plastic collapse or by cell wall fracture. According to the studies in [5, 24], honeycombs with 9 rows and 6 columns of cells are large enough to perform compressive tests without having significant edge effects. Here regular honeycombs with 11 rows and 9 columns of cells are adopted (see Figure 1b). Cell size needs to be chosen properly, because large cells increase specimen dimensions (for a given number of rows and

columns) and thus long printing time and high material cost, whereas small cells give rise to thin cell walls which may not be able to be printed. Here cell length is chosen to be 8 mm. To determine the thickness of the specimens, finite element analyses are performed, and specimens thinner than 12 mm are found to undergo out-of-plane buckling at some point during the process of compression (see Figure 2). Hence, we chose the thickness of honeycombs to be 20 mm. The geometry of the regular honeycombs was created in Creo CAD software. Specimens were printed along thickness direction. Compressive tests were carried out along the horizontal and vertical directions with three repetitions for each, thus 12 regular honeycomb specimens in total were printed.

Figure 2: (a) Deformation of a honeycomb with thickness of 6 mm during in-plane compression; (b) Deformation of a honeycomb with thickness of 12 mm during in-plane compression

2.3 Irregular honeycomb specimens

Two types of irregular honeycombs are considered here, namely, honeycombs of hexagonal cells but having wall thickness following prescribed log-normal distributions and honeycombs of uniform wall thickness but having cell size (diameter of incircle of cells) following prescribed log-normal distributions (see Figure 4). To make wall thickness or cell size following a distribution, a certain number of cells need to be contained in these honeycombs. However, as specimen size is limited by the maximum building volume of the 3D printer, the more the cells in the specimens are, the smaller the cell size is and the thinner the cell walls are. This could make it difficult for the camera to capture deformation at cell wall level and for the 3D printer to print. As a result, a trade-off between the number of cells and cell size is made for these specimens. For honeycomb specimens with non-uniform wall thickness, cell wall length is set to be 4.46 mm, and wall thickness follows a lognormal distribution, with the average being 0.446 mm and standard deviation being 0.1414 mm. The specimens are 172 mm wide, 170 mm tall and 25 mm thick. The honeycombs with cell size following a lognormal distribution have an average cell size of 4.46 mm with a standard deviation of 1 mm, and cell wall thickness of 0.3 mm. The specimens are 169 mm wide, 191 mm tall and 25 mm thick.

The geometry of irregular honeycombs was created using the commercial finite element software Abaqus using python scripts. Firstly, a precursor honeycomb without wall thickness (dashed line in Figure 3) is created. This is simple for honeycombs with non-uniform thickness, as each cell in them is hexagonal. For honeycombs with non-uniform cell size, the construction of the precursor honeycomb is indeed the creation of 2D Laguerre tessellations. The details of the generation of 2D Laguerre tessellations are given in [23]. Once the precursor honeycomb is generated, the points, lines, and cells are labelled and stored in a hierarchical order, so that the topologies can be readily known, i.e., which lines construct a cell and which points form a line. Thereafter, cell wall thickening is performed for all the cells one by one. To illustrate the thickening process, we take a cell ABCDE (see Figure 3) as an example. First we determine the inner normal of each edge of the cell ABCDE. As the thickness of

each wall is given, five linear equations which represent lines coincidental with inner edges ($A'B'$, $B'C'$, $C'D'$, $D'E'$ and $E'A'$) can be developed. Solving a set of two linear equations which represent two adjoining inner edges can yield the coordinates of an inner vertex, such as A' . Following the same process by rotation, the coordinates of the other four inner vertices (B' , C' , D' , E') are calculated. Each cell is analysed through this process, and then all the edges of cell walls are determined. With all the topological data obtained by this process, a sketch is drawn and extruded to 3D geometry in Abaqus. In this manner, three specimens for each type are designed.

Figure 3: Schematics of cell wall thickening

Figure 4: Printed honeycombs with (a) non-uniform wall thickness, and (b) non-uniform cell size

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile tests were performed with the printed dogbone specimens at 5 mm/min loading rate to characterize the properties of the printed material. Compressive tests were conducted for regular and irregular honeycombs with a synchronized camera facing squarely towards the specimens. In this section, the experimental results will be presented and discussed.

3.1 Properties of the printed material

Table 1 lists the average and standard deviation of modulus, ultimate tensile strength and elongation at break of the material printed in different orientations. It can be seen that the specimens printed standing up along y direction and those printed along z direction have tensile modulus slightly larger than that of the raw material, whilst the specimens printed lying along y direction have tensile modulus slightly smaller than that of the raw material. The ultimate stresses of the specimens printed

standing up along y direction and lying along y direction are slightly smaller than that of raw material, whereas the specimens printed along z direction exhibit ultimate stress 35.5% lower than that of raw material, which is attributable to the way of 3D printer making part by stacking materials.

	Modulus (Chord 0.05%- 0.25%) (GPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (standard) (%)
Lying along Y direction	2.05 ± 0.06	44.3 ± 0.36	3.98 ± 0.07
Standing up along Y direction	2.34 ± 0.03	45.9 ± 0.36	5.71 ± 0.42
Z direction	2.27 ± 0.03	31.6 ± 2.57	1.98 ± 0.30
Raw material [25]	2.17	49.0	8.3

Table 1: Tensile properties of the dogbone specimens printed along different orientations.

3.2 Response of regular honeycombs.

When the honeycombs with low wall thickness-to-length ratio (0.025) are compressed along vertical direction, the deformation is macroscopically similar to that of honeycombs exhibited in [5, 24], showing the spread of cell collapse in a row-by row manner (see Figure 5). However, in the present specimens, cells collapse by wall buckling; consequently cell walls remain curved (see Figure 5f) when cells are closed, different from that in [5, 24] where cell walls were nearly straight. This gives the honeycombs the ability to recover to their original shape when loads are removed. Unloading after a compression of 25 mm, it was found that the honeycombs recover with only 2% residual strain, as shown in Figure 9a. The measured yield strength and plateau stress of these honeycombs are 9.0 and 8.1 kPa, which are slightly higher than Gibson's prediction [1] which is 7.5 KPa. When compressed along horizontal direction, the honeycombs with low wall thickness-to-length ratio bulge out at sides (see Figure 6). The large deflection of cell walls causes the honeycombs behave nonlinearly. When the stress reaches around 10 kPa, cells walls in the middle area of honeycombs fracture and subsequently a flipped V-shaped band of collapsed cells was observed (see Figure 6).

Figure 5: Configurations of honeycombs with low wall thickness-to-length ratio at different times under compression along vertical direction (points a-f correspond to those in Figure 9a)

When the honeycombs with high wall thickness-to-length ratio (0.05) are compressed along vertical and horizontal directions, cell walls fracture rapidly through the honeycomb at an angle of 60° to compressive load (see Figure 7 and Figure 8), leading to a sudden drop in stress (see Figure 9b). The rupture strengths of the honeycombs are 58 kPa along vertical direction and 52 kPa along horizontal directions, which is close to Gibson's [1] prediction of 51 kPa. In summary, the response of honeycombs manufactured by 3D printers is the same as that of honeycombs made in conventional ways.

Figure 6: Configurations of honeycombs with low wall thickness-to-length ratio at different times under compression along horizontal direction (points A-F correspond to those in Figure 9a)

Figure 7: Configurations of honeycombs with high cell wall thickness-to-length ratio under compression along vertical direction: (a) before fracture, (b) after fracture

Figure 8: Configurations of honeycombs with high cell wall thickness-to-length ratio under compression along horizontal direction: (a) before fracture, (b) after fracture

Figure 9: Stress-strain curves of honeycombs with (a) low cell wall thickness-to-length ratio, (b) high cell wall thickness-to-length ratio under compression along vertical and horizontal directions.

3.2 Response of honeycombs with non-uniform wall thickness

To illustrate the deformation and failure progression in honeycombs with non-uniform wall thickness, configurations of one specimen at different times are presented in Figure 10. Figure 11 shows the stress-strain curve of this specimen, with the stresses and strains corresponding to the configurations in Figure 10 marked. When the honeycombs with non-uniform wall thickness are compressed, the deformations experienced by the specimens are not uniform, since each cell wall has different bending stiffness. For example, it is observed that cell walls enclosed by the ellipse in Figure 10a experience larger deflection than other areas. At some stage, cell walls begin to fracture (see Figure 10a), and the stress reaches maximum soon after fracturing starts (see Figure 11). Subsequently, cell wall fracture continues at multiple locations with stress decreasing. At some stage, many cells rupture simultaneously (see Figure 10e), creating a long ‘crack’ and a drastic reduction in the global stress (see Figure 11). When the cracks nearly cross the entire specimen, the stress becomes minimum (see Figure 10f and Figure 11). Thereafter, the ruptured cell walls come into contact and so the stress begins to rise.

It is noteworthy that in these honeycombs fracture always occurs to inclined cell walls (which are not aligned with compressive loads) as they suffer a larger bending moment, producing cracks along 60° to the compressive load. A crack propagates along weak links, such as thin inclined cell walls. However, the presence of thick cell walls may change the direction of crack propagation and even arrest crack propagation. The stress reaches maximum soon after first rupture of cell walls, and it becomes minimum when ‘cracks’ propagate across the entire specimen. The rupture strength of the specimens is 77 ± 4 kPa, and the compressive stiffness of the specimens is 4.9 ± 1.5 MPa. With

(a) Point A

(b) Point B

(c) Point C

(d) Point D

(e) Point E

(f) Point F

Figure 10: Configuration of honeycombs with non-uniform wall thickness at different times (points A-F correspond to those in Figure 11)

Figure 11: Stress-strain curve of a honeycomb with non-uniform wall thickness

Gibson's prediction, regular honeycombs with the same relative density have rupture strength of 384 kPa and elastic modulus of 12.8 MPa, which indicates that variation in cell wall thickness reduces the stiffness and strength of honeycombs significantly.

3.3 Response of regular honeycombs with non-uniform cell size

Similarly, the stress-strain curve of one specimen is shown in Figure 12 and the configurations of the specimen at point A, B, C, D, E and F are presented in Figure 13. When the honeycombs with non-uniform cell size are compressed, non-uniform deflection of cell walls are discernable as well. At a certain load, cell walls begin to fracture (see Figure 13b) and soon after the stress reaches its maximum value (see Figure 12). As compression progresses, cell walls fracture gradually and at multiple locations. The ruptured cell walls come in contact at some stage leading to a rise in stress. Eventually, a major crack is formed and crosses the entire specimen (see Figure 13f).

In this case, whether a cell wall fractures in early stage depends on the length of the cell wall, alignment with the compressive loading direction and configuration of cell walls surrounding it. Figure 14 shows the length and alignment angle to compressive load of the cell walls ruptured before point E. It can be noticed that the cell walls that are aligned within 30° to 60° and relatively long (maximum length is 9.5 mm) are more likely to fracture in the early stage. The exception is if a cell wall is surrounded by stiff cell walls, then the cell wall may not undergo fracture, because stiff cell walls can reinforce their neighbouring area and prevent adjacent walls from fracture.

The rupture strength of the specimens is 37 ± 4 kPa, and the compressive stiffness of the specimens is 996 ± 202 kPa. With Gibson's prediction, the regular honeycombs with the same relative density have rupture strength of 103 kPa and elastic modulus of 1.78 MPa, which implies that variation in cell size reduces the stiffness and strength of honeycombs significantly.

Figure 12: Stress-strain curve of a honeycomb with non-uniform cell size

Figure 13: Configuration of honeycombs with non-uniform cell size at different times (points A-F correspond to those in Figure 12)

Figure 14: Alignment angles and lengths of fractured cell walls

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, regular honeycombs and honeycombs with varying wall thickness and cell size (following lognormal distributions) were manufactured by a 3D printer. Compressive tests were performed for these honeycombs. During the tests with regular honeycombs, two typical failure modes of honeycombs, wall buckling and wall fracture, are demonstrated. The response of the printed regular honeycombs is found to be the same as that of conventional honeycombs. In irregular honeycombs, cell walls fracture gradually and in a scattered manner. Soon after the first failure of cell walls, the stress reaches maximum and then begins to reduce as more and more cell walls rupture. Fracture is more likely to occur in thin and long cell walls which are aligned with compressive load within 30° to 60° . In addition, the stiffness of neighbouring cell walls also affect whether a cell wall ruptures in early stage. The measured modulus and yield strength of the irregular honeycombs are far lower than those of the regular honeycombs with the same relative density.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Gibson, M. Ashby, G. Schajer, and C. Robertson, "The mechanics of two-dimensional cellular materials," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, vol. 382, pp. 25-42, 1982.
- [2] L. J. Gibson and M. Ashby, "The mechanics of three-dimensional cellular materials," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, vol. 382, pp. 43-59, 1982.
- [3] M. J. Silva, W. C. Hayes, and L. J. Gibson, "The effects of non-periodic microstructure on the elastic properties of two-dimensional cellular solids," *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, vol. 37, pp. 1161-1177, 1995.
- [4] A. Simone and L. Gibson, "The effects of cell face curvature and corrugations on the stiffness and strength of metallic foams," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 46, pp. 3929-3935, 1998.
- [5] S. D. Papka and S. Kyriakides, "In-plane compressive response and crushing of honeycomb," *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, vol. 42, pp. 1499-1532, 1994.
- [6] L. Gong and S. Kyriakides, "Compressive response of open cell foams Part II: Initiation and evolution of crushing," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 42, pp. 1381-1399, 2005.

- [7] W. Y. Jang, S. Kyriakides, and A. M. Kraynik, "On the compressive strength of open-cell metal foams with Kelvin and random cell structures," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 47, pp. 2872-2883, 2010.
- [8] A. Wilbert, W.-Y. Jang, S. Kyriakides, and J. Floccari, "Buckling and progressive crushing of laterally loaded honeycomb," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 48, pp. 803-816, 2011.
- [9] S. Gaitanaros, S. Kyriakides, and A. M. Kraynik, "On the crushing response of random open-cell foams," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 49, pp. 2733-2743, 2012.
- [10] L. J. Gibson and M. F. Ashby, *Cellular solids : structure and properties*, 2nd ed. Cambridge ; New York: Cambridge University Press, 1997.
- [11] V. S. Deshpande and N. A. Fleck, "High strain rate compressive behaviour of aluminium alloy foams," *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, vol. 24, pp. 277-298, 2000.
- [12] V. Deshpande and N. Fleck, "Multi-axial yield behaviour of polymer foams," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 49, pp. 1859-1866, 2001.
- [13] M. E. Kabir, M. C. Saha, and S. Jeelani, "Tensile and fracture behavior of polymer foams," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 429, pp. 225-235, 2006.
- [14] I. Daniel and J.-M. Cho, "Characterization of anisotropic polymeric foam under static and dynamic loading," *Experimental mechanics*, vol. 51, pp. 1395-1403, 2011.
- [15] M. A. Battley, A. M. Clark, T. D. Allen, and C. J. Cameron, "Shear strength of sandwich core materials subjected to loading rates relevant to water slamming," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, p. 0731684413509424, 2013.
- [16] C. Motz and R. Pippan, "Deformation behaviour of closed-cell aluminium foams in tension," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 49, pp. 2463-2470, 2001.
- [17] H. X. Zhu, J. R. Hobdell, and A. H. Windle, "Effects of cell irregularity on the elastic properties of 2D Voronoi honeycombs," *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, vol. 49, pp. 857-870, 2001.
- [18] J. L. Grenestedt and K. Tanaka, "Influence of cell shape variations on elastic stiffness of closed cell cellular solids," *Scripta Materialia*, vol. 40, pp. 71-77, 1998.
- [19] A. Simone and L. Gibson, "Effects of solid distribution on the stiffness and strength of metallic foams," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 46, pp. 2139-2150, 1998.
- [20] J. L. Grenestedt and F. Bassinet, "Influence of cell wall thickness variations on elastic stiffness of closed-cell cellular solids," *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, vol. 42, pp. 1327-1338, 2000.
- [21] I. Jeon and T. Asahina, "The effect of structural defects on the compressive behavior of closed-cell Al foam," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 53, pp. 3415-3423, 2005.
- [22] H. Yu, Z. Guo, B. Li, G. Yao, H. Luo, and Y. Liu, "Research into the effect of cell diameter of aluminum foam on its compressive and energy absorption properties," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 454-455, pp. 542-546, 2007.
- [23] Y. Chen, R. Das, and M. Battley, "Effects of cell size and cell wall thickness variations on the stiffness of closed-cell foams," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 2014.
- [24] S. D. Papka and S. Kyriakides, "Experiments and full-scale numerical simulations of in-plane crushing of a honeycomb," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 46, pp. 2765-2776, 1998.
- [25] Available: <http://www.3dsystems.com/au/materials/visijet-m3-crystal>